

THE EFFECT OF MOTIVATION, TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP, AND SOCIAL SUPPORT ON PERSONNEL PERFORMANCE THROUGH WORKLOAD PROPORTIONALISM IN THE EAST KALIMANTAN REGIONAL POLICE INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of work motivation, transformational leadership, and social support on personnel performance through workload proportionalism at the Narcotics Criminal Investigation Directorate (Ditresnarkoba) of East Kalimantan Regional Police (Polda Kaltim). The research employs a quantitative explanatory approach using Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with SmartPLS 3.3.9, involving 80 personnel as respondents selected through purposive sampling. Results indicate that work motivation, transformational leadership, and social support each positively and significantly influence workload proportionalism. Transformational leadership, social support, and workload proportionalism also significantly and positively affect personnel performance directly. However, work motivation does not directly influence performance, suggesting full mediation through workload proportionalism. Workload proportionalism partially mediates the effects of transformational leadership and social support on performance. These findings confirm that workload proportionalism is a critical mediating construct integrating Self-Determination Theory, Transformational Leadership Theory, and Social Support Theory in high-pressure organizational contexts.

Keywords: *Personnel Performance, Transformational Leadership, Work Motivation, Workload Proportionality, Social Support*

INTRODUCTION

The problem of drug abuse and trafficking is an increasingly complex global threat. The 2023 *World Drug Report* recorded that approximately 296 million people worldwide aged 15–64 have used drugs, a 23% increase over the past decade. Indonesia even ranked third in the world in drug transactions in 2021, with a prevalence of abuse reaching 1.95% of the productive-age population according to the National Narcotics Agency (BNN). This situation places the Indonesian National Police, particularly the Narcotics Investigation Directorate, at the forefront of high operational pressure. At the regional level, the Narcotics Investigation Directorate of the East Kalimantan Regional Police faces even more complex challenges. Its strategic geographic location, bordering Malaysia, extensive sea routes, and high labor mobility make this region a key international drug distribution route. In 2024, 1,774 narcotics cases were handled, with Samarinda and Balikpapan serving as the main entry points, and the distribution network is even beginning to reach the Indonesian Capital City (IKN) area. However, the high operational burden is not balanced by the availability of human resources, with a personnel deficit of 36%. This leads to an unequal distribution of cases, which impacts the perception of workload fairness and has implications for personnel motivation, satisfaction, and performance. From a performance management perspective, personnel performance is determined not only by technical capabilities but also by psychological and organizational conditions. One important factor is workload proportionality, namely the perception of fairness in the distribution of tasks based on capacity and competence. Based on *Equity Theory*, workload imbalance can cause stress, burnout, and decreased performance, while fair distribution can improve motivation and performance. This study examines three main factors that influence performance through workload proportionality: work motivation, transformational leadership, and social support. Based on *Self-Determination Theory*, intrinsic motivation plays a crucial role in improving performance,

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but can weaken when the workload is perceived as unfair. Meanwhile, transformational leadership can create a more equitable distribution of tasks through an understanding of individual capacity. On the other hand, social support serves as a stress buffer, reinforcing the perception that the workload can remain manageable proportionally. Although these three variables have been widely studied, studies in the context of the police, particularly the Narcotics Investigation Unit, are still limited. In addition, most studies have not included workload proportionality as a mediating variable that explains the mechanism of influence of these variables on performance. Therefore, this study offers novelty by integrating *Self-Determination Theory*, *Transformational Leadership Theory*, and *Social Support Theory* through workload proportionality as a mediating variable in one structural model. This study aims to analyze the influence of work motivation, transformational leadership, and social support on personnel performance through workload proportionality at the East Kalimantan Regional Police Narcotics Directorate. The results of this study are expected to provide theoretical contributions in the development of public sector organizational behavior studies, as well as practical contributions in the formulation of police HR management policies, particularly in creating fair task distribution, improving leadership quality, and strengthening social support to improve personnel performance sustainably.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship between work motivation variables and workload proportionality

Based on *Self-Determination Theory* (Ryan & Deci, 2000), the causal mechanism linking work motivation to workload proportionality can be explained through mutually reinforcing psychological pathways. Personnel with high intrinsic motivation characterized by the fulfillment of the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness tend to develop a work orientation focused on the task meaningfulness of *administrative* workloads. This orientation makes them evaluate the workload they receive not merely as pressure (*threat stressor*) but as a meaningful professional challenge (*challenge stressor*). Within the framework of *Equity Theory* (Adams, 1965), intrinsically motivated individuals have a higher tolerance threshold in evaluating the *input-output ratio*, so that an objectively heavy workload is still perceived as proportional as long as it is considered meaningful. Based on this mechanism, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: Work motivation has a significant positive effect on workload proportionality.

The relationship between work motivation variables and personnel performance

The causal mechanism linking work motivation to employee performance is rooted in psychological logic that can be explained step by step. Within the framework of *Self-Determination Theory*, intrinsic motivation, supported by the fulfillment of the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, produces a psychological state called *autonomous regulation*. This state enables employees to work because the task aligns with their values and professional identity, rather than because of external control. *Autonomous regulation* has been empirically proven to result in deeper work engagement, greater psychological resilience when facing operational obstacles, and consistent work quality over the long term (Good et al., 2022; Kumari & Kumar, 2023). In investigative tasks that often reach dead ends in the field, *autonomous regulation* prevents personnel from giving up. This state encourages active initiatives such as seeking new informants, developing intelligence networks, or updating operational strategies. Personnel working under autonomous regulation are less easily frustrated when initial approaches fail. They view failure as part of the learning process, not as a verdict of incompetence. This resilience stems from the belief that the work they do has a greater meaning than simply achieving administrative targets. Based on this mechanism, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2: Work motivation is not significant on personnel performance.

The relationship between transformational leadership variables and workload proportionality

The causal mechanism linking transformational leadership to workload proportionality can be explained through mutually reinforcing pathways within the framework of *Transformational Leadership Theory* (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Transformational leaders who actively consider the capacity, competence, and development needs of each individual through the dimension of *individualized consideration* will have an accurate understanding of each member's limits. This individual understanding provides an empirical basis for more objective and proportional task distribution decisions. When employees perceive that the assignments they receive truly take their capacity and competence into account, their perception of workload distributive justice improves significantly.

idealized influence, and *inspirational motivation* dimensions, strengthen this mechanism by establishing the leader's moral credibility. Transformational leaders, who are viewed as role models of integrity by their members,

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possess strong moral credibility to establish standards of fairness in task distribution as an organizational value. Personnel who internalize these standards of fairness tend to evaluate their workload through a more positive lens. They believe that the assignment process stems from fair and competency-based considerations, not from favoritism or seniority pressure. This trust stems from the consistency between the leader's words and actions, who has proven to prioritize the organization's interests over personal interests. Based on this mechanism, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3: Transformational leadership has a significant positive effect on workload proportionality .

The relationship between social support variables and workload proportionality

The relationship between social support and workload proportionality can be explained through a cognitive-affective pathway rooted in *Social Support Theory* (House, 1981) and *stress buffering theory* (Cohen & Wills, 1985). In the context of the Narcotics Investigation Unit, which structurally faces a 36 percent personnel deficit and a continuing surge in cases, an objectively heavy workload has the potential to be perceived as disproportionate and unfair. Strong emotional support from colleagues and superiors in the form of empathy, active concern, and recognition of personnel contributions has been shown to modify individuals' cognitive assessments of the workload. Personnel who feel cared for and appreciated by their environment tend to evaluate their workload through a collective lens rather than individual isolation. They perceive the burden as shared and supported by the entire team, thus maintaining a positive perception of proportionality despite the quantitatively heavy task volume (Mu et al., 2025).

This management of negative emotions is reinforced by the presence of concrete instrumental support. Tangible assistance in the form of equitable task distribution, the availability of investigative support resources, and easy access to information from experienced colleagues directly reduces the gap between task demands and available capacity. When personnel feel they do not have to shoulder the operational burden alone due to instrumental support from the team, evaluations of the fairness of workload distribution improve significantly (Ebrahimi et al., 2021). Instrumental support also includes the availability of adequate operational equipment, a supportive administrative system, and policies that enable personnel to work effectively without structural barriers. Based on these mechanisms, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H4: Social support has a significant positive effect on workload proportionality.

The relationship between transformational leadership variables and personnel performance

The variables linking transformational leadership to personnel performance can be explained through mutually reinforcing psychological and organizational pathways within the framework of Bass and Avolio (1994). Transformational leaders who are able to clearly and inspiringly articulate a vision for drug eradication will transform personnel's perceptions of their duties. This perception shifts from mere administrative obligations to morally meaningful devotion. This psychological transformation of meaning produces *autonomous motivation*, a drive to work rooted in the alignment of personal values with organizational goals, rather than solely in hierarchical pressures. *Autonomous motivation* has been empirically proven to produce more consistent and high-quality performance in the long term (Kumari & Kumar, 2023). Personnel who perceive their work as a moral calling tend to demonstrate a commitment that persists despite facing heavy operational pressures. Based on this mechanism, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H5: Transformational leadership has a significant positive effect on personnel performance.

The relationship between social support variables and performance

The variables linking social support to personnel performance can be explained through the framework of *Social Support Theory* and the *Job Demands-Resources* (JD-R) model. The Narcotics Investigation Unit is a work environment with very high *job demands*. Case volume continues to increase, pressure on investigative targets intensifies, and operational safety risks constantly lurk. In these conditions, social support functions as a *personal resource* that balances *job demands*, thus preventing personnel from being depleted of psychological energy before achieving optimal performance (Madzik et al., 2025). Personnel protected from *burnout* maintain the cognitive and motivational capacity necessary to consistently deliver high-quality performance. They remain able to think clearly and make sound decisions even under pressure. Emotional support from superiors and colleagues plays a crucial role in reducing operational anxiety levels. This anxiety includes concerns about legal risks in investigations, physical safety risks during field operations, and psychological stress from interactions with criminal networks. Personnel who feel emotionally supported tend to have greater psychological stability. They are less likely to become consumed

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by excessive worry that can disrupt concentration and analytical skills. Maintaining emotional stability allows cognitive functions to function optimally in high-pressure situations. Strategic decisions can be made more accurately because the mind is not clouded by anxiety. Based on this mechanism, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H6: Social support has a significant positive effect on personnel performance.

The Relationship between Workload Proportionality and Personnel Performance

Cognitive evaluations of fairness influence subsequent behavioral actions. When investigators perceive that the workload and operational responsibilities are distributed fairly and in accordance with their abilities, they will feel valued. This positive perception of proportionality prevents frustration or depression from arising (Ebrahimi et al., 2021). Psychologically, personnel free from feelings of unfair treatment will focus all their cognitive energy on completing tasks. This clear cognitive state triggers acceleration in legal filing and agile field maneuvers, thus leading to optimal individual performance (Fan et al., 2022).

H7: Workload proportionality has a significant positive effect on personnel performance.

The relationship between roles through the workload proportionality variable on the influence of work motivation on personnel performance

Workload proportionality acts as a critical mediator that transforms the influence of work motivation, transformational leadership, and social support on improving personnel performance (Fan et al., 2022). This mediating role works through optimizing available resources and efficiently distributing tasks, which in turn helps manage both physical and mental stress. A similar opinion was expressed by Ashkanani et al. (2022), who stated that workload proportionality contributes to improved performance through time efficiency and better output quality. Appropriate workload has been shown to increase employee motivation to complete tasks, which in turn has a positive impact on performance (Fajri & Terza Rahman, 2021). Conversely, when leaders are able to implement an effective leadership style that results in workload distribution according to employee capacity, productivity and performance can be significantly improved (Filiyan et al., 2025). The pressure caused by a high workload can be offset by good social support from coworkers and leaders, thus maintaining employees' quality of life (Ebrahimi et al., 2021). This is important because excessive workloads without adequate support have the potential to cause stress that interferes with performance (Carranza Esteban et al., 2023). Based on this description, it can be concluded that workload proportionality influences employee performance. Therefore, the following hypothesis is formulated.

H8: Workload proportionality has a significant positive effect through work motivation on personnel performance.

The Role of Workload Proportionalism in the Effect of Transformational Leadership on Personnel Performance

The mediation argument H9 explains why the influence of transformational leadership on performance is insufficient if it is merely inspirational without being accompanied by tangible managerial justice. Theoretically, transformational leadership produces two types of influence—motivational influence (through vision and inspiration) and structural influence (through individualized consideration that influences task distribution). Motivational influence alone is insufficient to produce optimal performance if it is not accompanied by structural influence manifested in tangible distributive justice. This is because there is potential for cognitive dissonance: leaders who convey an inspiring vision but in practice distribute the workload unfairly will lose credibility in the eyes of their personnel. Dissonance between leadership rhetoric and the reality of task distribution actually weakens trust, which is the foundation of transformational leadership effectiveness. Conversely, when the leader's individualized attention is manifested in concrete actions in the form of objective and equitable task distribution, leadership rhetoric becomes valid and trust is built. The proposed mediation pathway is: transformational leadership → workload proportionality (as evidence of leadership credibility) → performance. Proportionalism acts as a mediator that converts the influence of leadership from the inspirational level to the structural level that produces performance (Fan et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024), thus producing a hypothesis in the form of:

H9: Workload proportionalism mediates the significant positive effect of transformational leadership on personnel performance.

The Role of Workload Proportionality in the Influence of Social Support on Personnel Performance

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The mediation argument H10 explains the psychological mechanism linking social support to performance through workload proportionality. Based on Social Support Theory (House, 1981) and Equity Theory (Adams, 1965), the causal chain can be described in two stages. The first stage: social support—specifically instrumental support in the form of fair task distribution from superiors and coworkers—directly shapes perceptions of workload proportionality. When employees perceive that colleagues and superiors are there to help shoulder the operational burden, they reevaluate their input-output ratio (Equity Theory) and conclude that the task distribution they receive is fair and balanced. This means that social support not only functions as a stress buffer but also actively calibrates employees' perceptions of distributive justice. The second stage: this formed perception of workload proportionality then becomes a psychological mechanism that allows employees to fully allocate their cognitive and motivational energy to task execution, rather than processing frustrations caused by unfairness. This condition ultimately results in improved performance. Without the mediation of proportionality, social support only works through a temporary emotional pathway. With proportionality as a mediator, the influence of social support is transformed into structured and sustainable working conditions so that personnel performance can be maintained consistently (Sabrina & Ikhsan, 2023; Mu et al., 2025; Fan et al., 2022).

H10: Workload proportionality has a significant positive effect through social support on personnel performance.

Conceptual Framework of the Research

Information:

Straight Line () = Direct Relationship

Dashed Line () = Indirect-relationship

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative method with *explanatory analysis techniques* to test the relationship between variables based on hypotheses. This quantitative approach was chosen because this study aims to analyze the causal relationship (cause and effect relationship) between variables through numerical data collection and statistical analysis using data in the form of numbers obtained through questionnaires. The next process is a statistical analysis to test the formulated hypothesis with variables of the influence of work motivation, transformational leadership, and social support on personnel performance through workload proportionality as a mediating variable. This study aims to explain the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, by considering the role of mediating

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variables. The data analysis method used in this study is variance-based *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM), namely *Partial Least Squares* (PLS) using SmartPLS software version 3.3.9. The selection of the SEM-PLS method in this study is based on several main justifications. This study has a fairly complex structural model because it tests the relationship between many variables simultaneously, which includes three independent variables (Work Motivation, Transformational Leadership, Social Support), one dependent variable (Personnel Performance), and one mediating variable (Workload Proportionalism). Therefore, SEM-PLS is considered very appropriate and *robust* for analyzing models with multiple relationship paths simultaneously.

Data collection techniques are the researchers' methods for gathering complete data needed for a study, obtained from the research location in a comprehensive manner and related to the problem being studied. The data collection conducted in this study involved distributing questionnaires to respondents and conducting a literature review, which involved collecting data from various related journal articles, online news sources, and other data supporting the research. Questionnaires are designed to collect quantitative data that can be managed personally, sent, or distributed electronically to respondents. These questionnaires are generally more cost-effective and time-efficient than interviews and direct observation, but carry a high risk of non-response (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The measurement of variables in this study used a questionnaire instrument that was compiled based on a measurement scale that had been used and validated in previous research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULT

Direct Hypothesis Testing

Table 1 Direct Hypothesis Testing

Variables	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Social Support -> Personnel Performance	0.411	6,917	0,000
Social Support -> Workload Proportionality	0.437	8,794	0,000
Transformational Leadership -> Personnel Performance	0.424	7,293	0,000
Transformational Leadership -> Workload Proportionality	0.216	3,113	0.002
Work Motivation -> Personnel Performance	0.014	0.354	0.723
Work Motivation -> Workload Proportionalism	0.238	4,382	0,000
Workload Proportionality -> Personnel Performance	0.121	2,562	0.010

(Source: Processed Primary Data , 2026)

Indirect Hypothesis Testing

Table 2 Indirect Hypothesis Testing

Research Variables	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Social Support -> Workload Proportionality -> Personnel Performance	0.053	2,318	0.020
Transformational Leadership -> Workload Proportionality -> Personnel Performance	0.026	2,144	0.032
Work Motivation -> Workload Proportionality -> Personnel Performance	0.029	2,050	0.040

(Source: Processed Primary Data , 2026)

Summary of Hypothesis Test Results

Table 3 Summary of Hypothesis Test Results

H1	Work Motivation → Workload Proportionalism	0.238	4,382	Accepted
H2	Work Motivation → Personnel Performance	0.014	0.354	Rejected
H3	Transformational Leadership → Workload Proportionalism	0.216	3,113	Accepted
H4	Social Support → Workload Proportionality	0.437	8,794	Accepted
H5	Transformational Leadership → Personnel Performance	0.424	7,293	Accepted
H6	Social Support → Personnel Performance	0.411	6,917	Accepted
H7	Workload Proportionalism → Personnel Performance	0.121	2,562	Accepted
H8	Work Motivation → Workload Proportionalism → Personnel Performance (Partial Mediation)	0.029	2,050	Accepted
H9	Transformational Leadership → Workload Proportionalism → Personnel Performance (Partial Mediation)	0.026	2,144	Accepted
H10	Social Support → Workload Proportionality → Personnel Performance (Partial Mediation)	0.053	2,318	Accepted

(Source: Processed Primary Data, 2026)

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Work Motivation on Workload Proportionality

The results of this study revealed that work motivation drives a more positive perception of workload proportionality, reinforcing *Equity Theory* (Adams, 1965). This theory explains that individuals constantly compare the ratio between their contributions (*inputs*) and the outcomes *they* receive, using colleagues as a benchmark for fairness. In the context of Narcotics Investigation personnel, inputs can include time, effort, skills, and personal sacrifice, while outcomes include caseloads, operational responsibilities, and professional recognition. Personnel with high intrinsic motivation tend to have a greater tolerance for processing information related to workload. The internal drive to achieve and serve changes how they perceive the workload. The ability to perceive a heavy workload is a crucial cognitive mechanism. Internally motivated individuals do not view workloads solely as external pressure, but rather as opportunities to demonstrate competence and make a tangible contribution to drug eradication. This allows motivation to see through perceptions of unfairness, so that high workloads remain acceptable as long as they are perceived as meaningful and aligned with their professional goals.

The Influence of Work Motivation on Personnel Performance

The results of this study indicate that work motivation variables do not have a significant direct effect on personnel performance. This finding is interesting and important because it contradicts the common assumption that higher motivation leads to higher performance. In the management literature, a positive relationship between motivation and performance has long been recognized. For example, a meta-analysis by Good et al. (2022) showed that intrinsic motivation is a stronger predictor of performance than extrinsic motivation, as it results in deeper engagement and higher psychological resilience. Similarly, Wang et al. (2024) confirmed a causal relationship between work motivation and performance, where motivation has been shown to improve performance across different types of jobs and timescales. However, in the organizational context of the East Kalimantan Regional Police Narcotics Investigation Unit, this direct relationship was not proven. This indicates that in a highly hierarchical, procedural, and high-pressure work environment, personnel's internal drive cannot directly convert into performance

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without some intermediary mechanism. Furthermore, the results of this study align with the findings of Diana, Sulistyarningsih, and Hung (2022), who found that employee motivation does not directly impact *employee performance*, but does directly impact *employee engagement* and *job satisfaction*. This study also showed that *employee engagement* and *job satisfaction* fully mediate the effect of motivation on performance. Thus, these findings reinforce the view that work motivation does not always operate through a direct pathway; instead, it may require intermediary variables to achieve a significant impact on performance.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Workload Proportionality

Transformational leadership variables have been shown to have a positive influence on the workload proportionality of personnel at the East Kalimantan Regional Police Narcotics Investigation Directorate. This finding directly strengthens the theoretical framework developed by Bass and Avolio (1994), which states that transformational leaders are able to bring about positive change in organizations through four main dimensions: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. In the context of workload proportionality, the two most relevant dimensions are individual consideration and idealized influence, as both directly touch on aspects of distributive justice and the leader's credibility in the eyes of personnel. The individual consideration dimension contributes most significantly to the perception of workload proportionality. Leaders who actively consider the capacity, competency, development needs, and personal circumstances of each team member will have an accurate understanding of their respective limits. This individual understanding provides an empirical basis for more objective and proportional case distribution decisions.

The Influence of Social Support on Workload Proportionality

The social support variable was shown to have the most dominant influence on workload proportionality compared to other variables in this study. This finding reinforces the concept of the stress buffering mechanism popularized by Cohen and Wills (1985). Within this theoretical framework, social support does not directly reduce stress, but rather serves as a buffer that changes how individuals assess and respond to stressful situations. Personnel facing high workloads require support from coworkers and superiors who can change their cognitive assessment of the situation, from one initially perceived as a threat to a manageable challenge. This process of changing cognitive assessment occurs through two main pathways. First, emotional support in the form of empathy, caring, genuine attention, and recognition of personnel's contributions creates a sense of psychological safety.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Personnel Performance

variables on personnel performance have a positive influence and are very strong and firm variables in this study, that transformational leaders can improve performance by inspiring subordinates to go beyond personal interests for the benefit of the team and organization that transformational leaders can improve performance by inspiring subordinates to go beyond personal interests for the benefit of the team and organization Bass and Avolio (1994). This variable has an influence, where inspirational motivation comes from influential superiors and leaders who can explain a clear and compelling vision for drug eradication. This vision shifts personnel's perception from merely carrying out administrative obligations to a morally meaningful mission of service. This motivational shift results in autonomous motivation, a drive to work rooted in the alignment of personal values with organizational goals, rather than solely in hierarchical pressures. Personnel who interpret their work as a moral calling tend to demonstrate a commitment that persists even under heavy operational pressure.

The Influence of Social Support on Personnel Performance

Social support is a crucial variable in the Narcotics Investigation Unit. Social support serves as an external resource that protects personnel from the negative consequences of work stress through the buffering mechanism adopted by Cohen and Wills (1985). Social support does not directly eliminate stress, but rather alters personnel's cognitive assessment of stressful situations, so that heavy workloads are no longer viewed as destructive threats but rather as challenges that can be overcome collectively. In the Narcotics Investigation Unit, social support is a key factor in preventing personnel from experiencing excessive physical and emotional fatigue, as the unit faces safety risks, operational trauma, and investigative target pressure. Sukalova et al. (2022) in their study of law enforcement personnel found that social support negatively impacts burnout and positively impacts performance, with burnout partially mediating the relationship. Maintaining psychological stability allows personnel to maintain clear cognitive function to make critical decisions in the field, such as determining the right time to conduct a raid or assessing the credibility of information from an informant. Maintaining emotional stability in personnel allows cognitive functions

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to work optimally in high-pressure situations, so that strategic decisions can be taken more accurately because the mind is not clouded by excessive anxiety.

The Influence of Workload Proportionalism on Personnel Performance

The variable of workload proportionality on personnel performance has a strong positive influence based on Adams' Equity Theory (1965), this theory explains that individuals continuously compare the ratio between the contributions they make (input) and the results they receive (outcome), using coworkers as a benchmark for fairness. This tension motivates individuals to reduce this unfairness, often by reducing effort, reducing work involvement, or even showing counterproductive behavior that causes personnel to feel unfairly burdened and personnel will work carelessly or even personnel do not want to be responsible for the tasks given. Workloads are perceived as fair and proportional, and personnel's psychological energy is not wasted on managing frustration caused by injustice. This energy can be fully focused on substantive tasks, such as accurate investigations, gathering valid evidence, systematically compiling case files, and making swift tactical decisions in the field.

The Mediating Role of Workload Proportionalism in Influencing Work Motivation on Personnel Performance

The workload proportionality variable mediates the influence of work motivation on personnel performance, which is considered acceptable. These results indicate that although work motivation does not have a significant direct effect on personnel performance, work motivation still has an influence on performance when used through workload proportionality as an intermediary variable. These findings indicate that in the context of East Kalimantan Regional Police Detective personnel, work motivation is not yet strong enough to directly improve performance, but can be transformed into better performance when personnel feel that the workload they receive is distributed fairly, balanced, and in accordance with their capacity. This finding is supported by Ashkanani et al. (2022), who showed that the interaction between motivation and workload determines performance quality. A disproportionate workload erodes the positive impact of motivation on performance. This study's findings align with those of Diana, Sulistyarningsih, and Hung (2022), who found that motivation does not directly influence *employee performance* but instead works through mediating variables, namely *employee engagement* and *job satisfaction*.

The Mediating Role of Workload Proportionalism in the Influence of Transformational Leadership on Personnel Performance

The workload proportionality variable as a mediator in this study was proven to mediate the influence of transformational leadership variables on personnel performance, although the type of mediation as a whole was both direct and indirect. Thus, workload proportionality in this study was proven to play a role as a mediating variable that bridges the influence of transformational leadership on personnel performance. This finding indicates that transformational leadership will be more effective in improving performance if it is able to create a perception of fairness in the distribution of tasks and matters among personnel.

The Mediating Role of Workload Proportionalism in the Influence of Social Support on Personnel Performance

Workload proportionality, as a mediating variable in this study, was shown to mediate the influence of social support on personnel performance. These results indicate that social support not only directly influences performance but also indirectly through workload proportionality. These findings indicate that social support will be more effective in improving performance if it can shape the perception that the workload is distributed fairly, equitably, and in accordance with personnel capacity. Thus, social support not only functions as a source of psychological strength but also helps personnel interpret the workload as a reasonable and manageable responsibility. Theoretically, these results align with House's (1981) *Social Support Theory*, which explains that social support is an individual's perception that they are cared for, valued, and part of a network of caring relationships.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that: (1) Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on workload proportionality; (2) Work motivation does not have a direct effect on personnel performance; (3) Transformational leadership has a positive effect on workload proportionality and personnel performance; (4) Social support is the variable with the most dominant effect on workload proportionality and has a significant effect on personnel performance; (5) Workload proportionality has a positive effect on personnel performance; (6) Workload proportionality fully mediates the effect of work motivation and partially mediates the effect of transformational

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leadership and social support on personnel performance. This study provides theoretical contributions by integrating Self-Determination Theory, Transformational Leadership Theory, and Social Support Theory through a single mediating construct in the context of a high-pressure police organization. Key recommendations include reform of the competency-based workload distribution system, the continuous development of transformational leadership, and the institutionalization of the institutional social support system in the Narcotics Directorate of the East Kalimantan Regional Police.

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